

A factor 2 improvement in high-field dynamic nuclear polarization from Gd(III) complexes by design.

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ABSTRACT: Gadolinium(III) complexes have recently been demonstrated to have potential as polarizing agents for high field dynamic nuclear polarization (DNP) NMR spectroscopy. However, so far, Gd(III) complexes have yielded only modest ¹H signal enhancements of around a factor 10. By tailoring the ligand design to reduce the zero-field splitting (ZFS), we anticipate and demonstrate a quadratic improvement on DNP performance through the investigation of a stable, water soluble, narrow-line Gd(III) complex, [Gd(tpatcn)]. We measured ¹H signal enhancement up to 37 at 9.4 T and 100 K under magic-angle-spinning conditions, doubling the enhancement of the, so far, state-of-the-art [Gd(dota)(H₂O)].

Magic-angle-spinning (MAS) NMR is a well-established method to probe atomic-level structure and dynamics in solids.¹⁻⁸ However, a major bottleneck preventing wider use of the method is the inherently low sensitivity of NMR due to very low levels of polarization. Dynamic nuclear polarization (DNP) is rapidly emerging as an approach to overcome these limitations, where polarization is transferred from electron to nuclear spins, and the NMR signal can theoretically be boosted by up to a factor $\gamma_e/\gamma_n \sim 660$ for ¹H. In practice, the experiment depends on efficient microwave irradiation of the sample and the performance of electron containing polarization sources, usually at cryogenic temperatures (e.g. 100 K). In order to increase DNP enhancements, one of the recurring conundrums is to what extent it is possible to rationally improve the design of the polarizing agents (PAs). The most efficient PAs today for MAS-DNP are organic bis-nitroxides, or carbon-centered radicals, involving the cross effect or Overhauser effect mechanisms.⁹⁻¹³

For these, rational design has led to the synthesis of a plethora of compounds, yielding the gold-standard AMUPol¹⁴ and TEKPol¹⁵ families, and mixed radicals performing well at very high fields.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

However, nitroxides are not always compatible with sample formulations. For example, in reducing environments (such as those encountered in cells, or in many catalysts), bis-nitroxides are quickly decomposed and lose the capability to yield any DNP enhancement.¹⁹ An archetypal example is given in Figure 1 which shows the results of MAS-DNP experiments on a 1.3 M solution of ascorbic acid in glycerol-*d*₈:D₂O:H₂O (6:3:1 v/v). As expected, no signal enhancement is observed when AMUPol is used as the polarization source, since it is immediately reduced to a diamagnetic form, and EPR (Figure SI 5d) confirms that there is no free radical present in the solution. Indeed, ascorbic acid is often used as a nitroxide radical scavenger in dissolution DNP experiments.¹⁹⁻²⁰ The hyperpolarization of [1-¹³C]-ascorbic acid and [1-¹³C]-dehydroascorbic acid, the reduced and oxidized forms of vitamin C, has been reported in dissolution DNP experiments at 1.2 K using the trityl radical.²¹ However, the broad high field EPR line due to axially symmetric *g*-anisotropy for trityl hampers its efficiency. Thus the quest for efficient, very narrow-line, water soluble and stable PAs for high field MAS DNP.

There are currently very few alternative polarization sources at high field to the nitroxides.

Figure 1: MAS DNP spectra at 9.4 T, ~100 K and 12.5 kHz MAS via CP of a glycerol- d_8 :D $_2$ O:H $_2$ O (6:3:1 v%) solution of 1.3 M ascorbic acid and 8 mM [Gd(tpatcn)] in (a) and 10 mM AMUPol in (b). The microwave on and off spectra are in black and red respectively. The $\epsilon_{C CP}$ enhancements for the 1, 2, 3 ascorbic acid resonances is 24 for [Gd(tpatcn)] in (a) and 1 for AMUPol in (b). The other carbon resonances 4, 5, 6 are obscured by the glycerol peaks. Sidebands are indicated with asterisks.

Paramagnetic transition metal and lanthanide complexes can meet all the desired requirements. They have been extensively used in magnetic resonance, from protein tags for the determination of structural constraints and local information in NMR or EPR,²² to contrast agents (CAs) in MRI.²³⁻²⁵ In particular, we note that the complexes developed for *in vivo* MRI applications are by nature highly resistant to reducing conditions. High spin Gd(III) ($S=7/2$) and Mn(II) ($S=5/2$) based metal complexes have also been reported to achieve MAS-DNP enhancements at between 5 to 9.4 T.²⁶⁻²⁷ However, the best reported enhancements are around a factor 10 for ^1H at 100 K and 9.4 T, and so a key question is whether rational design strategies can be identified to improve efficiency of this class of potentially very important PAs.

Here we show that a Gd(III) complex, [Gd(tpatcn)] (1) (tpatcnH $_3$ = 1,4,7-tris[(6-carboxypyridin-2-yl)methyl]-1,4,7-triazacyclononane) can be efficiently used to polarize ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{15}N nuclei at 100 K and 9.4 T, in MAS-DNP experiments. We measured ^1H enhancements of up to 37, which is a factor two larger than for [Gd(dota)(H $_2$ O)] $^-$ (2) (dotaH $_4$ = 1,4,7,10-Tetraazacyclododecane-1,4,7,10-tetraacetic acid) which was so far the best Gd(III) PA (yielding ^1H enhancements of up to 19 in our hands). We attribute the higher enhancements to the nature of the ligand and the symmetry of the complex, which produce very narrow EPR lines, enabling more efficient saturation of the electronic transitions.

Figure 2: Chemical structures (a,b) and 3D representations of the coordination geometry of the lanthanide ion (c,d) of [Gd(tpatcn)]²⁸ (1) and [Gd(dota)(H $_2$ O)]²⁴⁻ (2). In (c), the coordination geometry of (1) is a slightly distorted tricapped trigonal prism with the pseudo- C_3 axis passing through the centre of the 1,4,7-triaza-cyclononane and the Gd(III) (in green) ion. In (d) the inner-sphere exchangeable water molecule coordinated with the complex is also indicated. Oxygen, nitrogen and hydrogen atoms are red, blue and grey respectively.

In general, there is a number of factors that might affect MAS-DNP efficiency, among which: ZFS²⁶⁻²⁷, concentration of the PA²⁹⁻³⁰, ^1H density of DNP matrix^{12, 31}, electronic relaxation times¹⁵, solvent accessibility³² and microwave field homogeneity in the rotor³³.

The first parameter, ZFS, is peculiar to high-spin complexes and is not present in nitroxide systems. Gd(III) ($S=7/2$) is a high-spin paramagnetic ion with seven unpaired electrons in the open 4f shell. The combined interaction of the Gd(III) ion with the ligand and between unpaired electrons, results in a zero-field splitting (ZFS) interaction expressed by the Hamiltonian:

$$H^{ZFS} = D \left(S_z^2 - \frac{1}{3} S(S+1) \right) + E(S_x^2 - S_y^2) \quad (1)$$

with S the total spin quantum number and D , E the axial component and rhombicity of the electron dipole-dipole interaction.

Specifically, the single-quantum satellite transitions involving states with $m_s = \pm 7/2 \leftrightarrow m_s = \pm 5/2$, $m_s = \pm 5/2 \leftrightarrow m_s = \pm 3/2$, $m_s = \pm 3/2 \leftrightarrow m_s = \pm 1/2$ are directly affected by ZFS, resulting in broad EPR lines. In contrast, the central transition $m_s = +1/2 \leftrightarrow m_s = -1/2$ is only broadened by the ZFS to second order, scaling proportionally to D^2/ω_{0s} , where ω_{0s} is the electron Larmor frequency, resulting in a narrower EPR transition (see Figure SI-6).³⁴

The dependence on D^2/ω_{0s} of the $m_s = +1/2 \leftrightarrow m_s = -1/2$ transition leads, in the limit of negligible alternative

broadening effects, to the conclusion that for a given reduction r of the ZFS, a gain in enhancement of the order of r^2 will be obtained (Equation S 7: $\varepsilon_{(1)}/\varepsilon_{(2)} \approx (D_{(2)}/D_{(1)})^2$).

Reduction of ZFS appears to be a powerful way to improve DNP for this class of PAs and can be accomplished by rational design of the ligand.

In complex **(2)** (Figure 2b,d), the dota⁴⁻ ligand is octadentate and the Gd(III) ion is nine-coordinate by the four nitrogen and the four carboxyl oxygen atoms of the ligand, with the remaining coordination site occupied by a single exchangeable inner-sphere water molecule. In contrast, in [Gd(tpatcn)] **(1)** (Figure 2a,c), the Gd(III) is nonacoordinate by the tpatcn³⁻ ligand (by three nitrogen atoms of the 1,4,7-triazacyclononane macrocyclic core, three nitrogen atoms of each pyridine moiety, and the three oxygen atoms of the carboxyl groups). All the coordination sites are occupied and there is no residual availability for the coordination of an exchangeable water molecule. The different coordination geometries result in different point group symmetry around the Gd center in the crystal structures, with [Gd(dota)(H₂O)]⁻ having pseudo-C₄ and [Gd(tpatcn)] being pseudo-C₃ symmetry. (Note that [Gd(dota)(H₂O)]⁻ exists as a mixture of two coordination geometries in solution.)³⁵⁻³⁶

The difference in symmetry between the two complexes, in association with the nature of donor atoms, leads to a significantly smaller ZFS in [Gd(tpatcn)]. The model of atomic contributions to ZFS described in the SI supports the smaller ZFS values in **(1)** than **(2)**.³⁷

Previous X- and W-band EPR studies³⁸ of **(1)** in solution at room temperature estimated the ZFS to be very small ($D=661$ MHz), while a recent study in frozen solution found an even smaller $D=485$ MHz.³⁷ We have determined the ZFS parameters from 10 K and 100 K EPR experiments at W-band using 25 μ M (standard EPR conditions) and 10 mM (standard MAS-DNP conditions) solutions.

Figure 3: Echo detected EPR spectrum for 10 mM **(1)** and **(2)** at 100 K, W-band, in glycerol-*d*₈:D₂O:H₂O (60:30:10 v%).

Figure 3 compares the EPR spectra for **(1)** and **(2)** at 100 K and shows that the central line of [Gd(dota)(H₂O)]⁻ is indeed broader. The main parameters extracted from the analysis of

the EPR lineshapes are given in Table 1 for 25 μ M. (See Table SI-4 for details of the fits and the parameter distributions). The ZFS parameters given are the ones at 10 K, as the ones extracted at 100 K are possibly underestimated due to anisotropic relaxation. As expected we find that the ZFS is a factor ~ 1.4 smaller for **(1)** than **(2)**, a trend that is seen at both 10 K and 100 K. In accordance with equation S 7, **(1)** is expected to provide a factor ($\sim 1.4^2 \approx 2$) better MAS-DNP enhancement than **(2)**.

Figure 4: (a) MAS-DNP enhancements measured for ¹³C,¹⁵N₂-urea for 5 mM solutions of **(1)** or **(2)** in glycerol-*d*₈:D₂O:H₂O (6:3:1 v%) at ~ 100 K and at the optimal field position for (negative) DNP. For ¹H the enhancements were measured on the carbon-13 signal of glycerol via CP³⁹. Further experimental details are given in the SI. (b) ¹H Zeeman field profiles for 5 mM of **(1)** or **(2)** in glycerol-*d*₈:D₂O:H₂O (6:3:1 v%). (c) ¹H-¹³C CP glycerol signals with/without microwaves for **(1)** at the maximum ¹H (negative) DNP enhancement.

Indeed Figure 4a clearly shows that the MAS-DNP enhancements recorded under 8 kHz MAS at 100 K with [Gd(tpatcn)] **(1)** are about a factor of 2 larger than those of [Gd(dota)(H₂O)]⁻ **(2)**, with the highest ¹H enhancements obtained here for [Gd(tpatcn)] being a factor 37. Direct ¹³C and ¹⁵N excitation with [Gd(tpatcn)] **(1)** yields MAS-DNP enhancement of respectively a factor 122 and 350.

Figure 4b shows the proton Zeeman field profiles for both complexes. The field position for the (negative) DNP effect is consistent with the similar isotropic g factors estimated to be 1.9918 for [Gd(dota)(H₂O)]⁻²⁶ and 1.9915 for [Gd(tpatcn)],³⁸ and in general with the relative independence of the electronic g -factor on the structure of the chelating ligand.³⁵ The Zeeman field profile in Figure 4 reflects indirectly the EPR line-shape at 9.4 T. In both cases it is very narrow, below 22 MHz. For comparison the linewidth of the

“narrow line” trityl radical is about 55 MHz at 5 T,²⁶ and gets broader at higher magnetic fields.

The optimal sample formulation has been investigated by varying the PA concentration. Intermolecular dipolar interactions, which represent an important broadening mechanism, are minimized at low concentrations. Therefore, we extensively investigated the range in between 1-12 mM. We actually have found the optimal concentration for [Gd(tpatcn)] to be 4 mM (Figure 5).

Figure 5: MAS-DNP ¹H enhancements via CP (ϵ_{CCP} numbers above the bars with 10% confidence interval) and polarization T_1 DNP build-up times (values in table in seconds, fits reported in SI) measured for solutions of (1) or (2) in glycerol- d_8 :D₂O:H₂O (6:3:1 v%) at PA concentration varying in between 1-12 mM at the optimal field position as in Fig. 2.

Figure 5 shows ¹H enhancements measured on carbon-13 (ϵ_{CCP}) for (1) and (2) in glycerol- d_8 :D₂O:H₂O (6:3:1 v%) at 115 K (measured by ⁷⁹Br T_1) with 8 kHz MAS, with the main magnetic field position determined via the Zeeman field profile experiment of Figure 4.¹ Compound (1) always returns a higher enhancement than (2) at any of the investigated concentrations. The ratio between the enhancements of (1) and (2) is on average around 1.9 which is in good agreement with the prediction of 1.95 detailed in SI and recalled above, corresponding to the square of the ratio between the ZFS axial values of the complexes (Equation S 7).

Table SI-3 suggests that increasing the ¹H density in the DNP matrix does not yield a better MAS-DNP enhancement.

Another parameter affecting MAS-DNP is the electronic relaxation behavior of the PA. We note that the change in coordination geometry leads to different relaxivity properties in solution.⁴⁰ Notably, long T_{1e} and T_{2e} have been clearly shown to allow for more efficient DNP (and are the key

factors in the performance of AMUPol and TEKPol)^{39,41}. A model developed for [Gd(tpatcn)] indicated long electronic relaxation T_{1e} and T_{2e} (both around 2·10⁻⁹ s) in solution at room temperature.²⁸ However, these conditions are far from those used for MAS-DNP at 100 K. We have measured T_{1e} and T_{2e} at W-band, 10 mM and 100 K (Table 1) and actually found that the $T_{1e} \cdot T_{2e}$ products are not different between the two complexes. This may not be surprising, considering that the relaxation mechanisms in solution and in the solid-state are expected to be completely different.^{22,42} We note that the intrinsic T_{1e} and T_{2e} of [Gd(tpatcn)] are very slightly longer than those of [Gd(dota)(H₂O)]⁻ at 25 μ M (Table SI 3).

We further note that the hyperfine interaction with the natural abundant $I=3/2$ nuclear spins ¹⁵⁵Gd (~15% n.a.) and ¹⁵⁷Gd (~15% n.a.) that contribute to additional broadening, is not resolved under the present experimental conditions.

An additional factor that we suggest to be relevant to MAS-DNP experiments is solvent accessibility to the PA region, which should affect how polarization is transferred from the electron into the surrounding frozen solvent nuclei. The expected increased solvent accessibility to the vicinity of the Gd(III) in (2) (which has a directly coordinated water molecule) compared to (1) (which does not) is confirmed by pulsed EPR ESEEM experiments (details in SI), and leads to the conclusion that in these systems solvent accessibility plays a more minor role than the change in ZFS.

Previously, it has been shown that addition of dielectric particles to frozen solutions can improve the overall microwave field strength and homogeneity in the sample and return better MAS-DNP enhancements for both cross effect and Overhauser effect based PAs.⁴³⁻⁴⁴ Here, incorporation of manually-ground sapphire particles improves the ¹H DNP enhancement by over a factor 2 (Figure SI-3). This suggests that the microwave field homogeneity in the 3.2 mm sapphire rotor is currently also one of the limiting factors for the observed MAS-DNP enhancements in Gd(III) based polarizing agents, where the mechanism for transfer is the solid effect (see Figure SI-4).

Table 1. T_{1e} and T_{2e} measured for (1) and (2) in glycerol- d_8 :D₂O:H₂O (6:3:1 v%) at W-band (~94.1 GHz), 100 K, 10 mM and the corresponding saturation factor $T_{1e} \cdot T_{2e}$. The last column reports the ZFS D value (in MHz) at 25 μ M and 10 K. The distribution σ_D is given in parenthesis with the corresponding confidence interval according to the model described in the SI.

Complex	$T_{1e}/(\mu\text{s})$	$T_{2e}/(\mu\text{s})$	$T_{1e} \cdot T_{2e}/(\mu\text{s})^2$	$D(\text{MHz})$ ($\sigma_D(\text{MHz})$)
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¹ The enhancements, but not their ratios, in Figure 5 are about 30% lower than those observed in Figure 4 for both (1) and (2). We attribute this to the presumably higher sample temperature for the spectra of Figure 5 (due to reduced cooling N₂ gas flow capacity of 28 L/min vs the ideal 35 L/min) and to possibly non-optimal microwave irradiation (due to ice formation over time in the probe waveguide).

[Gd(tpatcn)]	0.7±0.1	0.32±0.06	0.22±0.07	525±30/(174±72)
[Gd(dota)(H ₂ O)] ⁻	0.7±0.1	0.32±0.05	0.22±0.07	733±64/(270±134)

In summary, we have shown that [Gd(tpatcn)] gives the highest MAS-DNP enhancements for high-spin complexes reported so far, up to a factor 37 for ¹H and 350 for ¹⁵N at ~100 K and ~9.4 T. Despite the similarity in the *g*-factor and the *T*_{1e}·*T*_{2e} product, and the better solvent accessibility for [Gd(dota)(H₂O)]⁻, we find a factor two better MAS-DNP performance for [Gd(tpatcn)] compared to [Gd(dota)(H₂O)]⁻, that we attribute to the lower measured ZFS parameters. This improved performance is demonstrated over a wide range of concentrations between 1-12 mM, with best performance being obtained at relatively low concentrations. This in turn is attributed qualitatively to the symmetry of the complex together with the possibly lower ligand field of [Gd(tpatcn)] due to the differences in the coordination sphere. We note that [Gd(tpatcn)] performs a factor 10 better than [Gd(dtpa)(H₂O)]²⁻, which has a factor 3 larger reported ZFS than [Gd(tpatcn)]²⁶. These results all agree with the prediction that DNP enhancements should increase quadratically as ZFS decreases and suggest further improvement is possible through rational ligand engineering of metal complexes in the future. Perhaps most importantly, [Gd(tpatcn)] provides a versatile, efficient, narrow-line, water soluble, stable DNP polarizing agent that is resistant to reducing conditions (Figure 1), fully addressing the initial quest.

Supporting Information. Additional experimental details can be found in the supporting information for dynamic nuclear polarization enhanced NMR spectroscopy and EPR spectroscopy.

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TOC Graphic

